

PROJECT SUMMARY

Overview:

Biogeographical regionalization, macroecology, software development, user workshops, new tools;

The analysis of species occurrences to group geographical areas based on their shared biotas is integral to evolutionary biology. However, the statistical software to analyze and manipulate the massive species data has not been fully developed. Historically, classifications of biogeographic regions were based on descriptions of the ecology, taxonomic composition or vegetation features of regions. Recent approaches provided more quantitative, and objective classifications, but broadly recapitulated earlier efforts and overlooked the evolutionary implications captured by the shared phylogenetic relationships of species. Despite the massive availability of phylogenetic trees and species distribution records, statistical and replicable computational infrastructure to analyze and manipulate such massive amounts of data have not been fully developed. Because biogeography has traditionally developed as an observational science rather than an experimental one, developing replicable analytical tools for biogeography into reproducible workflows is critical. Our R software package *phyloregion* – designed for biogeographic regionalization and macroecology – can overcome these computational challenges. It contains tools for biogeographical regionalization, macroecology, conservation, and visualization, and has potential application in diverse fields including evolution, microbial diversity, systematics, ecology, phylogenetics, and many others.

In this proposal, we plan to substantially increase computational efficiency of functions in *phyloregion*, to add new functionality, and create a model for user-guided software development in biogeography.

Intellectual Merit:

The project will accomplish the following: (1) Develop and implement new tools in *phyloregion* for biome evolution and biogeographical investigations. Novel Grade of Membership model that represents sampling units as partial memberships in multiple groups will be established to analyze large biogeographic datasets; (2) Develop new tools in *phyloregion* to visualize patterns of biogeography, macroecology and evolution. *Phyloregion* will be enhanced to pass objects between R and RevBayes (a C++ tool for Bayesian phylogeography) for phylogeographic visualization through R; and (3) Develop new tools in *phyloregion* for conservation that reflect the key dimensions of phylogenetic diversity including richness, divergence and regularity. Research on these objectives has the potential to unlock important avenues for new research in unanticipated ways.

Broader Impacts:

Phyloregion is already widely used and represents one of only a few biogeographical resources in R tailored for megaphylogenies and macroecological datasets. This research will create new, open-source, and freely distributed software tools with potential for transformative impact in biogeography and beyond. We will use workshops and conferences for dissemination, and to provide introduction to intermediate R coding and implementation of biogeographical tools. Workshops will target a mix of faculty, postdocs, and especially graduate and undergraduate students, who will be trained on the use and application of *phyloregion* in their research, and to help develop their own novel biogeographic functions to assemble into an R package. We will work with existing diversity programs at Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi and Southeastern to recruit diverse undergraduate participants, and provide resources for them to learn about graduate school. All products from this project will be disseminated free and open-sourced through computer codes, publications, conferences, workshops and vignettes. *Phyloregion* vignettes will be used to create an upper-division course for undergraduate and early graduate students. The grant will support the mentoring of one postdoctoral researcher and a graduate student and many undergraduates. Women and traditionally underrepresented groups will be specifically encouraged to apply for the postdoctoral research position, as well as for the workshops.

A. Overview.

Collaborative Research: *phyloregion*, computational infrastructure for biogeographic regionalization and macroecology in the R computing environment

The analysis of species occurrences to group geographical areas on the basis of their shared biotas is central to macroecology and evolutionary biology. However, compared to the mass production of species occurrence records and phylogenetic data, tools that can analyze these datasets in a reasonable amount of time are almost non-existent or do not scale well in terms of computer time and memory or other resources. This is particularly true when there are many taxa, and geographic regions to examine. As a consequence, many questions that are critical to the fields of ecology, biogeography and evolutionary biology, are simply out of reach for scientists without the right analytical tools.

Our recently developed open-source R package *phyloregion* – designed for biogeographic regionalization, and macroecology – can overcome these challenges. *phyloregion* is already widely used and represents one of only a few biogeographical resources in R that is tailored for megaphylogenies and macroecological datasets. It contains tools for biogeographical regionalization, macroecology, conservation, and visualizing biodiversity patterns, and has potential application in diverse fields including evolution, microbial diversity, systematics, ecology, phylogenetics, and many others.

We will substantially enhance *phyloregion* to increase computational efficiency for dealing with large scale macroecological datasets and megaphylogenies, and improve the package's engagement with users via feedback gathered from our workshops. Proposed research activities include the development and implementation of new tools for biome evolution and biogeographical investigations, new tools to visualize patterns of biogeography, macroecology and evolution. From these research outputs, we will develop new methods for guiding conservation prioritization, and will host several biogeography-method users' workshops to train students in the theory and application of these methods using *phyloregion*.

B. Results from Prior NSF Support.

B.1. Barnabas H. Daru (PI). “Collaborative Research: Leveraging historical collections and new surveys to characterize foundational shifts in vital symbioses in the threatened Arctic” *Award* #2031928. *Period*: 2020-2023. *Total Amount*: \$143,676. Intellectual Merit: Discovery of fungal endophytes in plants and lichens of the Arctic to understand how endophyte communities changed over time with implications for climate change. Broader Impacts: Commitment to inclusively train and diversify the next generation of biodiversity scientists, and contributing broadly to science, education, and society. New award, nothing yet to report.

B.2. April M. Wright (PI). “NSF Postdoctoral Fellowship in Biology FY 2016” *Award* #1612858. *Period*: 2016-2017. *Total Amount*: \$136,000. Intellectual Merit: The project explored the use of morphological data in divergence time estimations. Broader Impacts: This included both the production of scientific software for phylogenetic estimation and theoretical work to understand the role of incomplete lineage sampling in fossil-based phylogenetic work. Publications and Products: Four publications¹⁻⁴, and three conference presentations.

C. Rationale.

Biogeographical regionalization is the grouping of geographic areas on the basis of their shared biotas⁵, and it is crucial for understanding the ecological and historical processes affecting species distribution and prioritizing conservation⁶⁻⁸. By integrating phylogenetic information into the delineation of biogeographic regions, we can identify areas where organisms share close evolutionary ties, despite sharing few species in common^{6,7}. For instance, a phylogenetic

regionalization approach can aid in capturing biotas missed by traditional regionalization schemes such as the newly defined Panamanian, Sino-Japanese, and Oceanian realms for terrestrial vertebrates of the world⁷. Biogeographic regions can reflect transition zones⁹. Such regions are of significant evolutionary importance because they represent places where different evolutionary lineages coexist and provide sources for novel species interactions^{10,11}, and potentially high diversity¹². Additionally, patterns of phylogenetic regionalization can provide insights into evolutionary mechanisms such as dispersal, speciation, extinction and niche conservatism shaping large-scale biodiversity patterns¹³. However, many of the aforementioned questions, critical as they might seem to the study of biogeography and macroecology, are simply out of reach for scientists without the right analytical tools¹⁴.

Needs Assessment (computational challenges): The species occurrence data typically used for biogeographic regionalization are generated from massive digitization of museum records and citizen science campaigns and are often available as point records, polygons or raster layers, whereas phylogenies are derived from throughput of nucleotide sequencing efforts, which increase the size of biodiversity databases many-folds. This exponential increase in species occurrences and phylogenetic information inflates the size of running time for clustering algorithms^{15,16}, and consequently increases the challenges for visualizing downstream biodiversity patterns. In **Fig. 1**, the number of terminal taxa on phylogenetic trees has increased over time. Where phylogenetic studies used to have a few dozen tips, a few thousand tips are now common. This poses computational challenges for researchers. For phylogeographic analyses, for instance, researchers rapidly run into a matrix exponentiation problem. If the tip taxa occupy three biogeographic regions in the modern-day, there are 64 possible ancestral geographic ranges (extirpation and occupation of two or more ranges must be considered). In an ordinary molecular phylogenetic model, the state space is four, by contrast. Computing probabilities across a 64-possibility matrix is a challenge, and the largest matrix that can be handled with established exponentiation methods is about 20 areas. Such large-scale analysis can easily reach thousands of bytes and analysis using current tools would be prohibitively expensive computationally. Research tools for analyzing data sets of this scale do not exist. In order for this field to flourish, new ones will need to be developed^{17,18}.

Similarly, enhanced visualization tools are not merely a convenience. As biologists shift from point estimates of solutions to Bayesian methods, more sophisticated ways of visualizing solutions to appropriately quantify uncertainty and confidence in a given solution is required. In a given analysis, a focal solution such as a summary phylogeny, and the sample of trees from which this summary was computed may need to be displayed. Numerous ways of visualizing uncertainty in phylogenetic trees, such as cloudograms and densitrees¹⁹, are available. However, this becomes more difficult when additional features, such as ancestral ranges are visualized alongside the phylogenetic tree. Extending capabilities to visualize solutions to include spatial dimensions will allow researchers to have a fuller sense of the uncertainty in their solutions.

Presently, the software most commonly used for analysis of biogeographical regionalization and macroecology includes: BiotaPhy²⁰, picante²¹, ape²², betapart²³, biodiverse²⁴, and BioGeoBEARS²⁵. These packages contain some statistical capabilities by integrating phylogenetic information and biogeographic data and methods. For instance, BiotaPhy facilitates integration, data collection and analysis by connecting to existing data repositories such as the Open Tree of Life, iDigBio, and Lifemapper. However, these packages differ in their biogeographic inferences, and analytical and computational capacity to process the massively mobilized megaphylogenies and occurrence records spanning tens of thousands of species across regional to global spatial extents. Some of these packages are developed for use in command-line while others are graphical user-interface (GUI). Most packages are developed to address a specific biological question and have restricted analytical options that can limit computational flexibility. As a result, scientists wishing to address more complex hypotheses will have to use a compilation of disparate computational workflows that are difficult to reproduce. Further, most of the available tools have well known shortcomings in terms of memory allocation and handling large datasets. Recent approaches to scale existing software to handle the exponential growth of biodiversity datasets include developing parallel algorithms²⁶ and using modern computational architectures, such as multicore systems, GPUs, and supercomputers²⁷. Although these methods provide reproducible source codes, they require the user to have a good background in high performance computing, making them difficult to be extended by the user community. Also, since the raw data commonly used for macroecology and biogeography analysis are typically represented as a dense matrix of 1s and 0s, they tend to be prevalent with many zero values because organisms have unimodal distributions along ecological gradients²⁸. Consequently, analyzing every element of such matrix can be computationally challenging. To overcome this drawback, we propose the use of a sparse matrix²⁹, a matrix in which only the non-zero elements are stored and used for downstream analysis. This can mitigate memory space and computing restrictions.

Given the aforementioned needs assessment, our recently developed open-source and freely available R package *phyloregion* (*l'fy-lo-ridʒən*)³⁰ can overcome these computational challenges. *phyloregion* is designed to facilitate analysis of biogeographic regionalization, and macroecology, is already widely used and represents one of only a few biogeographical resources in R that is tailored for megaphylogenies and macroecological datasets. The package is available freely for direct installation through R from the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN), while the development version is hosted on GitHub. Indeed, *phyloregion* is the only package that has the capability to conduct complete analysis of biogeographical regionalization from input community distribution data and phylogenetic tree to calculations of compositional turnover through to visualization of the generated patterns in geographic space (Fig. 2). Compared to available packages, *phyloregion* is several times faster and allocates less memory because it can utilize a sparse matrix by holding only the non-zero elements of a community matrix. This makes it ideal for analysis of alpha diversity metrics (including evolutionary distinctiveness, phylogenetic

endemism, and phylogenetic diversity) as well as beta diversity, i.e., differences between local communities, to cluster very large species occurrences into biogeographic regions. For instance, when we benchmarked *phyloregion* against other packages in analyses of alpha diversity metrics such as phylogenetic diversity and phylogenetic endemism as well as for analyzing compositional turnover (e.g., beta diversity and phylogenetic beta diversity), we found that *phyloregion* is faster and more efficient in memory allocation than other packages (Table 1).

Developing biogeographic inference software to run in the R environment has many advantages. R has a long history of supporting reproducible research, which means that data and code used to make findings are available and are sufficient for an independent researcher to recreate the findings³¹. Another advantage of reproducibility of R is that it is becoming a standard to judge scientific claims³². In addition, R has an incredible range of graphical libraries which can facilitate complex visualizations of biogeographic patterns, phylogenetic trees, and maps³³. Finally, most analyses of biogeographic patterns and underlying process have already been implemented in R²⁵. Adding to the capabilities of biogeographic inference in this environment will enhance the establishment of a paradigm for related approaches in the modern age of biogeography.

Table 1. Benchmarking *phyloregion* against available software packages for analysis of alpha and beta diversity of plants in southern Africa (n = 1400 species).

	Packages	Memory allocation (MB)	Speed (s)
Phylogenetic diversity	<i>phyloregion</i>	1.83	0.00287
	<i>hilldiv</i>	170.22 (x 93)	1.09 (x 380)
	<i>pez</i>	60.79 (x 33)	0.13 (x 45)
	<i>picante</i>	59.5 (x 33)	0.12 (x 42)
Phylogenetic endemism	<i>phyloregion</i>	1.06	0.0036
	<i>pez</i>	498.93 (x 471)	1.89 (x 525)
Beta diversity	<i>phyloregion</i>	0.40	0.0010
	<i>betapart</i>	0.60 (x 1.5)	0.0011 (x 1.1)
	<i>vegan</i>	1.02 (x 2.6)	0.0013 (x 1.3)
	<i>BAT</i>	31.76 (x 79)	0.044 (x 44)
Phylogenetic beta diversity	<i>phyloregion</i>	1.07	0.0051
	<i>betapart</i>	1240 (x 1159)	2.14 (x 420)
	<i>picante</i>	1240 (x 1159)	4.38 (x 859)
	<i>BAT</i>	207.39 (x 194)	1.61 (x 316)

reproducibility of R is that it is becoming a standard to judge scientific claims³². In addition, R has an incredible range of graphical libraries which can facilitate complex visualizations of biogeographic patterns, phylogenetic trees, and maps³³. Finally, most analyses of biogeographic patterns and underlying process have already been implemented in R²⁵. Adding to the capabilities of biogeographic inference in this environment will enhance the establishment of a paradigm for related approaches in the modern age of biogeography.

Engaging user community in early stage design: Gathering user feedback on provisional design concepts early in the design process has the potential to create a robust piece of cyberinfrastructure that fulfill user needs³⁴. We applied a user-centered approach in the design of *phyloregion* to elicit feedback from users on the early design concepts and throughout the development. **Engaging users from the beginning allows the incorporation of useful feedback into future designs and to establish a strong connection with a well-demonstrated need that will have more impact on the user community.** Here, we highlight examples of how we have demonstrated a need for *phyloregion* by the user community in the early stage design.

Workshops: workshops are an effective technique for early stage software design across many disciplines³⁵. All the PIs of this proposal have experience running workshops on biogeographic or phylogenetic methods in R. For instance, PI Daru gave an R workshop in biogeographical regionalization and conservation using *phyloregion* at the Jan. 2020 conference of South African Association of Botanists in Free State, South Africa. A total of 32 students from institutions across South Africa attended the workshop. Since then, students from the workshop have been reaching out with feedback and comments regarding using the package in their research, which have been helpful in improving and developing future versions of the package. Wright and Schliep have been involved with running an R workshop for intermediate R users to learn package development practices. These workshops have resulted in the publication of several R packages^{36,37}.

Social media and GitHub outreach: Each PI of this project maintain an active blog for their R package (*phyloregion*, *phangorn*, *treedata.table*, and *paleotree*) on GitHub, which represents an enormous resource portal for the biogeographic and macroecology community. For instance, PI Daru's *phyloregion* blog³⁸ allows direct deployment of analysis vignettes to pkgdown³⁹, *Twitter* (305 followers), *Ecology in R Facebook group* (10,857 members) and *Biogeography Facebook group* (6,800 members). These vignettes sometimes provide updates to the package's functions, or describing entirely new methods, others are bugs about *phyloregion* or R biogeographic

packages. The feedback ('comments' or 'likes' from social media, and 'pull requests' from GitHub) showed that these vignettes were perceived as novel, timely, and needed by the user community.

Activity in user community: All the PIs have been very active in the R user community for biogeography, ecology or phylogenetics by contributing to the email list-serves and blogs. For instance, Daru is active in the *R-sig-geo* and *Stack Overflow* communities, whereas Schliep is a regular contributor to the *R-sig-phylo* group, often responding to *R-sig-phylo* queries. In many cases, queries may result in bug fixes, updates, improvements, or the production of new functionality in any of our packages.

Monthly CRAN downloads: Another demonstrable need of the package in the user community is that *phyloregion*, although a new R package (published online in Sep. 2020), already has over 500 monthly downloads and 1 citation (as of Oct. 2020) and a growing user pool. This suggests that the package is helpful for the biology community.

We intend to maintain this level of community engagement at every design stage of the package. Consequently, to expand *phyloregion's* capabilities, considerable effort is required to enhance and develop the package so that *phyloregion* remains at the cutting edge of biogeography, macroecology, and evolution.

D. Design and implementation.

One of the most important endeavors in recent decades is the rapid rise in the digitization of species occurrence records from natural history museums and phylogenetic trees from high throughput DNA sequencing efforts. These resources have the potential to thrust biogeographic investigations to the forefront of biodiversity research. These records can also provide a window into the past to assess how geographic regions, biomes, and communities are assembled through time, are currently maintained and how they may evolve in the future⁴⁰. However, these resources are underused largely due to the lack of analytical tools that can harness the value of these massively mobilized data. This proposal will facilitate the expansion of the computational capabilities of the *phyloregion* R package to enhance analysis of biogeographic regionalization and macroecology. For the proposed research, *phyloregion* will serve as a preliminary foundation to build upon, as a proof-of-concept for techniques that work and as a guiding direction to improve the usability, performance, and dissemination of the software to the user community. This grant, if awarded, will be used to develop: 1) innovative approaches and strategies for inferring biome evolution, 2) visualization tools to be used by domain scientists, and 3) next-generation computational tools for guiding conservation prioritization. Because these axes correspond to areas of significant method deficit, we believe that this project has the potential for transformative impact on biogeographic investigations and macroecology. In the paragraphs below, we describe each objective, provide its background, preliminary work, and an outline of the proposed research.

Objective 1. Develop new tools for biome evolution and biogeographical investigations

Background. Inferring patterns of biogeography can provide a window into the historical processes by which present-day biota arose and how they may evolve in the future. Although fossil data provide perhaps the most direct insights into the dynamics of the evolutionary past, such as speciation and extinction⁴¹, it is often sparse for many taxonomic groups. Dated phylogenetic trees derived from DNA sequences can serve as a surrogate for detailed fossil data, and help to unravel the mechanisms shaping regional species pools at different temporal and spatial scales⁴²⁻⁴⁵. More recent phylogenetic analyses have revealed the importance of dispersal, biogeography, extinction, speciation and past climates in explaining the origin and distribution of present-day biological diversity on a global scale (e.g.⁴⁶⁻⁵³). For instance, the available phylogeny-based ancestral range estimation methods (**Fig. 3A**) provide explicit frameworks for addressing uncertainty by extrapolating evolutionary relationships from measured functional traits of lineages

back to their ancestors^{22,54,55}. Such approaches, although indispensable, were not originally developed for biogeographic analysis *per se* and can be inherently problematic when it comes to handling large datasets or coding geographic character states (e.g., biomes). Traditionally, biomes are often coded by assuming that a species is either present or absent in a biome without accounting for its intermediate membership, i.e., a species can have partial membership in more than one biome. Moreover, compared to the exponential increase in species occurrences and phylogenetic trees⁵⁶, the tools that can analyze these datasets to infer biome evolution in a reasonable amount of time do not scale well (in time, memory or resources).

A second method for inferring biome evolution is provided by slicing a dated phylogenetic tree at successive time depths through the phylogenetic tree to gain insight into the evolutionary past of present-day diversity of mammals. We develop a similar framework in *phyloregion* to explore the origin of contemporary biogeographic regions in southern Africa, but here we successively remove phylogenetic structure in the tree (**Fig. 3B**)

linking the woody plant species in the regional flora to identify the evolutionary depth at which biogeographic regions collapse into each other⁵⁸. The phylogenetic depth at which biogeographic regions become indistinguishable may indicate the time at which they differentiated historically. A third approach for inferring biome evolution is through reconstruction by cross-taxon surrogates (where some taxonomic groups can serve as surrogates to infer the evolutionary history of more poorly known taxa) (**Fig. 3C**). For instance, the origin of the African savannas has been variously inferred using several proxies such as dated phylogenetic trees of C₄ grasses⁶⁰⁻⁶², underground geoxyllic suffrutex trees⁶³ and the evolution of early hominin species⁶⁴. Not only do these proxies point to different dates on the origins of these biomes, they used different analytical methods, suggesting a need to harmonize the methods for inferring biome evolution.

Preliminary data. The first step in analysis of biome evolution is to generate a distance matrix of beta diversity³⁰. This is a memory-intensive operation and a bottle-neck for available algorithms. To this end, we developed a method in *phyloregion* that uses a sparse matrix to efficiently compute pairwise dissimilarity matrices for large community data and phylogenetic trees on widely used dissimilarity indices such as Simpson, Sorensen, and Jaccard⁶⁵. We contrasted the performance of *phyloregion* with comparable packages (including *picante*, *vegan*, *betapart*, **Table 1**) for analysis of (phylogenetic) alpha and beta diversity metrics using an empirical dataset of the flora of southern Africa that includes species distributions and phylogenetic relationships for 1,400 plant taxa (data from⁶). We found that *phyloregion* is several orders of magnitude faster and

efficient in memory allocation than other packages (**Table 1**). We then implemented an algorithm in *phyloregion* (function *timeslice*) that slices a dated phylogenetic tree at successive time depths back in time by collapsing younger phylogenetic branches into older ones to infer the origins of species assemblages (see **Fig. 3B**). At each phylogenetic depth, we compare the newly generated phylogenetic clusters to the original clusters estimated using the fully resolved phylogeny. This allows us to explore the phylogenetic depth at which the spatial signature of present-day biogeographic assemblages emerges (**Fig. 3B**). A similar approach is also implemented in the R package *paleotree*⁵⁷ by collaborator Bapst. When paired with our sparse matrix approach, the *timeslice* function is very fast, allocates less memory and can handle megaphylogenies of any size and complexity. We will use our preliminary work on time-slicing phylogenetic tree as a starting point which shows enormous time- and space advantages.

Proposed research. With the support of this grant, we propose to develop methods for geographical range evolution to overcome two most critical challenges in ancestral area reconstruction: i) defining ancestral areas for the reconstruction, ii) handling big datasets. We will explore the potential of the Grade of Membership model (sometimes referred to as Latent Dirichlet Allocation) for biogeographic regionalization and biome evolution (**Fig. 4**). Common clustering approaches e.g., hierarchical or k-means cluster analysis, are best suited for detecting abrupt changes in composition^{8,66-68}, but may fail to detect potentially novel species interactions such as the gradual intergradation of the regions. The Grade of Membership model, originally devised for text-mining but now used in community ecology, can represent sampling units as having partial membership in multiple groups^{69,70}. It produces easily interpretable results, reflecting the

underlying associations between species, branch lengths, or functional groups that admix to form local communities. This feature is important because it can allow the decomposition of assemblages into abrupt or gradual turnover along ecological gradients obviating the need to arbitrarily assign biomes to species,

Fig. 4. Workflow to identify biogeographic regions using a Grade of Membership model. (A) Community matrix (optionally paired with phylogeny or functional traits) is (B) analyzed using a Grade of Membership Model which allows the units of analysis (i.e., species or regions) to have partial membership in multiple clusters. (C) This generates values of omega (cluster contribution per grid cell) and theta (species' contribution per cluster) as outputs. (D) Biogeographic regions are visualized using piecharts that represent the proportional contribution of species to grid cells.

which has been the standard approach so far^{69,70}. The second major challenge lies in the ability of existing tools to handle large datasets. To date, the majority of the existing methods for inferring ancestral areas for species are viable for small datasets. Our methods will provide convenient functions for converting the input community data (commonly derived from polygons, point records or raster layers) to condensed sparse matrices²⁹ or triple sparse matrices²⁹, thereby facilitating fast computations of large datasets.

Research in biome evolution for this grant proposal will thus focus on these two identified challenges: assigning species based on biogeographic regions that reflect the natural grouping of species in geographic space, and handling biogeographic datasets of ever-increasing size and complexity. We will develop new methods for exploring biome evolution for datasets of varying sizes, from small to massive datasets spanning thousands of taxa and covering a wide geographic extent, from regional to global extents. Next, we will implement our *timeslice* method in a

biogeographic framework by pairing it with the Grade of Membership model to infer biome evolution at any scale and for any taxonomic group. These functions will also draw from existing data sources by writing algorithms that utilize an application programming interface (API) to tap into major data hubs including the Open Tree of Life⁷¹, and Timetree⁷² for phylogenetic data, and Map of Life⁷³, Global Biodiversity Information Facility⁷⁴, Integrated Digitized Biocollections, and Botanical Information and Ecology Network⁷⁵ for biogeographic data. Collaborator Bapst has experience writing functions in his R package *paleotree* to utilize an API for pulling external data from the Paleobiology Database (e.g., `example(paleotree::plotPhyloPicTree)`).`

Objective 2: Develop new methods for visualizing biogeographic patterns

Background. Biogeography is predominantly a visual science, meaning that observations such as discontinuous species distributions, altitudinal or latitudinal diversity gradients are frequently expressed in maps, graphs and/or pictures⁷⁶. As biodiversity data becomes larger in terms of the amount of species occurrence records and phylogenetic trees, and analytical tools become more sophisticated, the challenges for visualizing biogeographic patterns also increase. This necessitates a program that can easily and quickly analyze large input files and generate outputs that can be used for downstream analysis. Although *phyloregion* is one of only a few biogeographical resources in R tailored for very large biogeographical datasets, it is still in need of robust visualization interface and enhanced documentation for users. Here, we propose to develop user-friendly methods implemented in *phyloregion* that make analysis and visualization of biogeographic patterns and macroecology more accessible to a wide range of researchers.

Preliminary data. Some methods for visualizing patterns of biogeographic regionalization already exist in *phyloregion*³⁰. For instance, the function *plot.phyloregion* differentiates among phyloregions using colors in multidimensional scaling (MDS) space to project the amount of phylogenetic turnover of clades in different phyloregions. Unlike traditional approaches which arbitrarily assign random colors to phyloregions, our MDS coloring approach displays the phylogenetic relationships among phyloregions such that phyloregions with similar colors have similar clades and those with different colors differ in the clades they enclose. Similarly, the function *plot_swatch* (also in *phyloregion*) maps discretized values of a quantity using continuous color gradients, for visualizing various biodiversity metrics ranging from phylogenetic diversity, phylogenetic endemism, to maps of evolutionary distinctiveness depicting the mean phylogenetic turnover between a

phyloregion and all other phyloregions in the study area^{7,13}. **Fig. 5** illustrates examples of the available tools in *phyloregion*³⁰ for visualizing relationships among phyloregions in geographic space (function *plot.phyloregion*), in multidimensional scaling color space (function *plot_NMDS*) and as map of evolutionary distinctiveness (function *plot_swatch*) based on hierarchical cluster analysis for woody plants of southern Africa (data from⁶). We have already implemented all the methods used to generate **Fig. 5** in *phyloregion*⁶.

A major drawback of visualizing patterns of phylogenetic regionalization using (hierarchical) cluster analysis is that their results may be difficult to interpret particularly for large datasets spanning many taxa or geographic regions. Existing approaches are often suited for assigning species assemblages into a single group^{7,8,68}, but may not differentiate between soft and hard

boundaries when in fact these boundaries intermix to some extent and are not so clearly delineated for many taxa. A major improvement of the user experience would be to extend the Grade of Membership model to be visualized using pie chart maps (**Fig. 4D**) to reflect the decomposition of assemblages into abrupt or gradual turnover along ecological gradients^{69,70}.

Proposed research. We propose to develop new functions for *phyloregion* that allow visualization of biogeographic regions to reflect the natural intergradation of species assemblages. A conceptual of this idea is provided in **Fig 6**. In this hypothetical example (**Fig. 6A**), the boundaries

between bioregions in X show sharp taxonomic progression in species composition indicating evolutionary distinctiveness whereas the boundaries in bioregions Y or Z intergrade into each other, indicating transition zones. Additionally, the user may wish to create stacked barplots (commonly called structure plots in population genetics software) to visualize soft or hard boundaries across biogeographic regions (**Fig. 6B**). To implement this idea, we will use the output from the fit of Grade of Membership model (**Fig. 4**). The Grade of Membership model will take a sparse community matrix as input and give *theta*

Fig. 6. Illustration of propose biogeographic regions using (A) piecharts in geographic space, and (B) structureplots, to depict intergradation of regions.

and *omega* as outputs. Omega corresponds to cluster contribution per grid cell, whereas theta is species' contribution per cluster. Thus, we will use omega to create piechart maps (**Fig. 6A**) to visualize the resulting biogeographic regions with each segment of the pie indicating proportional contribution of species to sites. Additionally, we will use omega to create structure plots to visualize hard or soft boundaries (e.g., **Fig 6B**). We expect this to greatly facilitate comprehensive communication of biogeographic patterns.

In Year 2, we will focus effort on the challenging problem of plotting massively mobilized biogeographic data for species distributions, and phylogenetic information, spanning thousands of taxa and across broad geographic extent. This will be achieved by developing algorithms for *phyloregion* that utilize an API to connect to public open-access repositories such as GBIF, Map of Life, Tree of Life, BIEN (see **Objective 1**). Since biogeographic patterns are scale dependent, varying along spatial grains, geographic extents and taxonomic treatments^{13,77,78}, we will create zoomable maps differentiating among phyloregions in which the resulting biogeographic patterns are likely to be dependent on the scale of interest set by the user. Our tools will allow users to zoom in and out of geographic regions to reveal hidden patterns, and we will create methods to effectively summarize patterns and processes underlying biogeographic regionalization for subregions. For instance, Elliott & Davies⁷⁹ showed that analysis of biogeographical regionalization at a more granular geographic scale reflects ecological processes such as biotic interactions, competition and short-distance dispersal that can easily be missed over large spatial scales. To our knowledge, these methods have not been implemented in software. We propose to create new tools to quantify and visualize the amount of spatial structure in the distribution of organisms at the community level and how this structure can be related to patterns of biogeographic regionalization at large scales. Additionally, we will develop an interactive GUI for *phyloregion* to enhance fast exploratory data analysis allowing users to explore plotting different variables. The GUI will also provide the ability to select/deselect subsets of species pool, clades, and subregions in real time. To implement this concept, we will use the *shiny* package⁸⁰, a GUI and web-based application that allows users to build beautiful, responsive and powerful

applications and visualizations from R. We will develop the interactive biogeographic GUI for each of the statistical summary plots available in *phyloregion*, including maps of evolutionary distinctiveness, continuous gradient plots, ordination plots, structure plots and piechart maps. Ultimately, these visualizations and GUIs will enhance the user experience thereby facilitating comprehensive understanding of biodiversity patterns.

Additionally, biogeographic analyses are increasingly performed in a Bayesian framework⁸¹ often using the phylogenetic software *RevBayes*^{82,83}, and rarely in R. Bayesian phylogeography introduces some challenges: instead of one solution, users compute a distribution of solutions (the posterior sample⁸⁴). Users will typically compute a summary visualization or solution for their posterior samples, but the distribution of solutions in the sample itself is important. However, summarizing these data is notoriously more difficult⁸⁵. To make Bayesian phylogeography more accessible for researchers, we propose to create wrapper functions for *phyloregion* to facilitate visualization of posterior traces of solutions, as well as summary statistics. *RevBayes* is a C++ software that provides crucial distributions and inferential infrastructure, allowing users to build custom models and analyses. It implements a flexible programming language called Rev. The language is similar to R, but the two languages do not share any programmatic infrastructure. The wrapper functions would enable code and analysis objects to be passed between Rev and R (*phyloregion*). Since Rev has no graphics engine, this would be a useful advance, allowing Bayesian phylogeographers to take advantage of R's advanced plotting capabilities.

Objective 3. Develop computational tools for guiding conservation prioritization

Background. As extinction rates increase with global change, the disparity between extinction crisis and available conservation resources increases. It is therefore crucial to identify conservation priorities to maximize returns on limited resources^{86,87}. Traditionally, conservation efforts have been prioritized based on species-level metrics (e.g., species richness, endemism and threat)⁸⁷⁻⁸⁹. These metrics alone fail to detect the substantial evolutionary and conservation implications captured by the shared phylogenetic relationships and evolutionary distinctiveness of species⁹⁰⁻⁹². Recent approaches harmonized metrics that consider evolutionary components, for example, phylogenetic diversity⁹³, evolutionary distinctiveness⁹², phylogenetic endemism⁹⁴, or a combination of these metrics. Indeed, Tucker et al.⁹⁵ reviewed 70 different phylogenetic diversity (*phylodiversity* henceforth) metrics commonly used in conservation, community ecology and macroecology. These plethora of phylogenetic metrics from which to choose for maximizing conservation (reviewed in ref.⁹⁵), only complicate conservation efforts; for instance, different metrics are sometimes used to address similar questions. Additionally, the alternative open-source phylogenetic tools for ecology and conservation (such as *picante*²¹, *pez*⁹⁶, *hilldiv*⁹⁷) have well known shortcomings in terms of memory allocation and handling large datasets compared to *phyloregion* (**Table 1**). Nonetheless, phylodiversity can inform real-world conservation planning. For example, the Australian government intends to expand conservation areas through collaboration with researchers, and land owners, to identify conservation areas based on phylogenetic information⁹⁸. Other agencies e.g., Conservation International, intends to incorporate evolutionary heritage in their conservation activities⁹⁹. Indeed, PI Daru is a member of the Phylogenetic Diversity Task Force of the International Union for the Conservation of Nature, advocating for the preservation of evolutionary diversity. Determining what to value for setting conservation priorities therefore requires the development of an evidence-based tool that is transparent, reproducible, and defensible for the decision-making process. These metrics can be streamlined into standard R analysis workflows.

Preliminary data. We have demonstrated the utility of *phyloregion* in mapping standard conservation metrics of species richness, weighted endemism and threat as well as fast computations of phylodiversity measures such as phylogenetic diversity, phylogenetic endemism, and evolutionary distinctiveness and global endangerment. The major advantage of these

functions compared to available tools e.g., *biodiverse*²⁴, is the ability to utilize sparse matrix that speeds up the analyses without exhausting computer memories, making it ideal for handling large datasets. Additionally, *phyloregion* features breakthroughs in data transformations from a traditional dense or long community format to a sparse matrix derived from the package *Matrix*¹⁰⁰.

Proposed research. We propose to expand the tools for analysis in biodiversity conservation. Specifically, we will develop algorithms that reflect the phylogenetic dimensions – richness, divergence, and regularity – that can be used for addressing fundamental questions in biology at multiple ecological scales. For instance, among the richness metrics Faith’s phylogenetic diversity, the sum of branch lengths⁹³ – receives more attention than metrics that capture pairwise phylogenetic distances (e.g., phylogenetic species richness¹⁰¹ or phylogenetic isolation¹⁰²). The latter two will be developed in this study. For metrics that calculate divergence such as mean pairwise distance separating taxa in a community or mean nearest taxon distance commonly used in community ecology¹⁰³, we will develop functions that are faster and memory efficient to handle pairwise distance analysis separating taxa at any scale ranging from small communities to large macroecological and biogeographical scales. Metrics of phylogenetic regularity that calculate the regularity or evenness of species on a phylogenetic tree, have remained largely unexplored in terms of analytical tools¹⁰³, and therefore will be developed in *phyloregion* in this study.

Null models are crucial for separating patterns from processes and for contrasting against alternative hypotheses in ecology and conservation¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁷. However, compared to the exponential growth of biodiversity data, methods for randomizing community data matrices and phylogenetic trees to parse out biogeographic patterns from underlying mechanistic processes remain poorly developed. We propose to develop new algorithms for computing biogeographic null models to reflect the major dimensions of phylodiversity alongside their spatial features (range size, grain size, spatial extent). This will be implemented by extending the sparse matrix approach to enhance fast randomization of large community data matrices spanning thousands of sites and taxa to reflect various null models of species co-occurrence including *frequency*, *richness*, and *trialswap*²¹ plus algorithms to facilitate shuffling the tips in megaphylogenies.

Sometimes, conservation efforts might want to prioritize the representation of species or clades as an insurance mechanism particularly when the number of species is large as opposed to simply most diverse areas¹⁰⁸. Along these lines, complementarity methods, which attempt to include the maximum number of unrepresented species or phylogenetic branch lengths (i.e., phylogenetic diversity-complementarity) in an area, offer a more powerful approach for identifying a minimum conservation network that includes all species or phylogenetic branches of interest¹⁰⁹. However, none of these methods have been developed as software. With this grant, we propose to develop tools that integrate phylogenetic information and apply complementarity methods which can be used for reserve designs or build network of protected areas. For phylogenetic diversity-complementarity for instance, the algorithm will be developed in a way that it will first find among sites that contribute the most phylogenetic diversity, then move to subsequent sites and calculate phylogenetic diversity for branch lengths that were not spanned in the previous sites. Such an approach can ensure complete representation of biodiversity in tandem with the identification of most diverse areas (e.g., hotspots) that improve the connectivity of conservation areas.

E. Project Management.

Here, we describe the personnel responsible for all major tasks, milestones for judging productivity as well as the timeline of our research and broader impacts activities over the three-year course of this grant (**Fig. 7**). PI Daru and collaborator Schliep are the original developers of *phyloregion* and comprise the *phyloregion* team. They currently maintain the package. Since its development in 2020, they have been implementing suggestions and feedback from *phyloregion* users which has improved the package. To this end, the team is aware of aspects of *phyloregion*

in need of further development, and will use their combined experience developing biogeographic tools and implementing them in software (e.g., *ape*²², *phangorn*¹¹⁰) to ensure the successful execution and completion of Objectives 1 (**Biome evolution**), 2 (**New visualization tools**) and 3 (**Conservation**). Collaborator Bapst maintains an R package *paleotree*⁵⁷, which is widely used for paleontological and phylogenetic analyses. His expertise in writing R functions to use an API for pulling external data will be leveraged to ensure successful completion of Objective 1 (**Biome evolution**). Co-PI Wright has expertise in developing phylogenetic tools and implementing them in software, the most recent being *treedata.table*³⁷, an R package for efficient manipulation of phylogenetic trees and data. Her qualifications will be leverage to ensure successful completion of Objectives 1 (**Biome evolution**) and 2 (**New visualization tools**). Further, all the (co-)PIs and collaborators have experience in teaching and organizing R workshops. Combining our complementary knowledge, experience, and unique perspectives will enable us to successfully complete the proposed workshops (**Broader Impacts**). The project will support the training of one postdoctoral researcher, a graduate student and several undergraduate students in research related to the project. The project will also provide training on cutting-edge methods in biogeography, ecology, and evolution for several users during the workshops in Years 1-3. Throughout the grant cycle, we will maintain regular communication by email and tele-conferencing to track progress.

F. Broader Impacts.

Broader Impacts. The experience of the PIs involved in this proposal demonstrates that collaborations between creators of scientific software that underpins biological research can unlock important avenues for new research. In particular, our efforts outlined above will set a paradigm for next generation biogeographical investigations, and further demonstrate the value of comprehensive biogeographic investigations for understanding the origin and distribution of biodiversity. Along these lines, our proposed outreach will create a set of educational initiatives targeting undergraduate and graduate students in the United States who are pursuing biogeographic and macroecology research.

We additionally request funding to create a biogeography-method users workshop with collaborating scientists Schliep, Wright, and Bapst annually for all three years of the grant term. The proposed workshops will be held at TAMUCC's Laguna Madre Field Station in south Texas in Years 1 and 3 and Turtle Cove Field Station, Louisiana in Year 2 (see letters of collaboration). Each of these themed workshops will be 10 days long and targeted to the three objectives of our proposal: **New methods for inferring biome evolution** (Year 1), **New visualization tools for biogeographic regionalization and macroecology** (Year 2), and **New tools for guiding conservation prioritization** (Year 3). We will select 10 learners for our workshop. These learners will be selected from a range of career stages, but focusing on undergraduates, graduate students and postdocs. Ideally, these students will be selected for ability to program in R and at least some knowledge of biogeography and macroecology. Selected students will be asked to arrive with a dataset of their own, or with an idea for a biogeographic project in R.

Throughout the 10 days, the PIs will alternate giving lectures on intermediate topics in R programming in relation to biogeography, macroecology and evolutionary biology. A summarized syllabus of the workshops is illustrated in **Fig. 8**. The PIs will use package development best

practices, such as those recommended via the ROpenSci code review organization, to generate intermediate-level tutorials to guide participants to creating their own or contributing to an R package. The remainder of the course will be dedicated to students developing their own novel biogeographic functions to assemble into an R package, and to receive feedback from peers and the PI team. Along with the package, they will be asked to produce documentation for the package in the form of a vignette. One vignette will be of lesson material that could be used in an undergraduate classroom.

Day	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
1	R basics	Mapping phylogenies	Tidying & Filtering data
2	R Functions and debugging	Spatial Data with R	Phylodiversity metrics
3	R Markdown & GitHub	Graphics, maps	Biodiversity hotspots & coldspots
4	Data types: points, polygons, rasters, phylogenies	Data visuals with ggplot2	Complementary algorithms for reserve design
5	Open science + reproducible research	Coordinate reference systems	Networks and Protected areas
6	R programming	Leaflet, Structure plots, pie map	Spatial grain and extent
7	Biome evolution in R	Introduction to <i>shiny</i>	Area of occupancy
8	Simulation methods	Best practices	Extent of occurrence
9	Your first R package	R Markdown & GitHub	Case studies
10	Student project presentation	Student project presentation	Student project presentation

Fig. 8. Syllabus of workshop topics.

Additionally, undergraduate participants will be invited to a special session every evening of the workshop. These sessions will cover applying to graduate school, finding the right fit of graduate programs, and funding for early career researchers. Undergraduate participants will be selected from underrepresented backgrounds. This set of lessons will be envisioned as an undergraduate diversity in computing preview. Wright has experience recruiting research personnel via the Upward Bound and Gear-UP programs at Southeastern Louisiana University (Southeastern). These programs also exist and will be leveraged at TAMUCC for recruitment of undergraduate participants (Upward Bound and McNair Scholars). To greatly expand access and participation, these workshops will also be webcast for other interested parties to participate.

All new functions will either be incorporated (with full credit to the authors) into *phyloregion*³⁰ or authors will be encouraged to publish it on their own. Participants will be encouraged to publish via the ROpenSci organization, which conducts peer review of R packages. This will ensure high-quality workshop outputs. Manuscripts from ROpenSci packages are also fast-tracked to be published open-access at *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, and participants will be encouraged to pursue this avenue. As each team will produce a vignette that could be used for undergraduate instruction, at the end of the workshop, the teams will lead the rest of the participants in a tutorial. This will help spot weaknesses in each lesson. At the end of three workshop cycles, this will result in a robust set of tutorials that can be assembled into an undergraduate course. These workshop materials will be published in the free and open access *Journal of Open Source Education*, which publishes open access lesson materials (e.g., see ref¹). This will enable the course to be adopted more widely. During year 3, Daru and Wright will finalize these materials into an undergraduate biology course and teach it for the first time. Because this course will be a hands-on exploration of biogeography in R, funds for a one-year subscription to RStudio Cloud are also requested to ensure that all learners have access to the same R environment, and that access to a personal laptop does not hinder any individual's participation in the class. This is particularly important, as both Southeastern and TAMUCC have high percentages of students classified as low income by Pell status (43% and 49%, respectively).

The PI team will also mentor one postdoctoral researcher for the three years of the project (see **Postdoctoral Mentoring Plan**). For this position we will actively recruit a researcher with expertise that is complementary to the PI team. For instance, we will hire a postdoc with experience implementing spatial and phylogenetic methods for biogeography. The postdoctoral researcher's effort will be concentrated on **Objectives 1, 2, and 3**: methods for inferring biome evolution, new visualization tools, and conservation, respectively. In addition, we request funding to support one graduate student. The student will work with the PI team and the postdoctoral

researcher on one or more of the proposal **Objectives**. We will target a student with an empirical biogeography focus and interest in method development and application. The PI team and postdoctoral researcher will mentor the student on biogeographic inference methods, cutting-edge spatial analysis, and software development. The student will be a teaching assistant for the annual biogeography-method users' workshop. ***With the support of this grant, the PIs of this project will reciprocally, enhance their scientific and analytical skills in programming, statistics, biogeography and macroecology.*** The proposed activities including teaching and mentoring students and postdoctoral fellow will facilitate the expansion of the PIs' experience in these areas as well as promote research collaboration.

Products. Beyond this outreach, each of the **Objectives** in our proposal will generate products with broader relevance to the community. Outside of the papers that we intend to publish for each **Objective**, the efforts from this proposed research will be a significantly enriched computational infrastructure, *phyloregion*, that powers biogeographical research in the R computing environment. This will include improved documentation and vignettes for easy access, which are crucial to ensuring reproducibility and functionality of the package. *phyloregion* is already a dynamic package with capabilities for preparing different data types (point records, polygons, rasters, phylogenies), analysis of alpha and beta diversity as well as visualizing the results of biogeographical regionalization, depending on the research questions. All the products and methods developed in this study will be made open-source and freely distributed.

G. Communication and Dissemination.

All the products from our efforts will be disseminated to the scientific community through peer-reviewed publications, conference presentations, workshops and analysis vignettes as follows: 1) *Peer-reviewed publications:* We propose to submit several articles for publication based on this project. For instance, our first publication will focus on describing new methods for integrating the Grade of Membership model for biogeographical regionalization and other investigations. A second publication will apply the new biome inference tools for biome evolution using empirical data of the world's vascular plants. We will then publish an updated software note for *phyloregion*, describing new functionality available within the package. 2) *Conferences:* PIs Daru and Wright will present the findings from this project in at least one international conference per year (e.g., useR!, or International Biogeography Society). 3) *Workshops:* In addition to the proposed biogeography workshops in Years 1-3 (see **Broader Impacts**), we will lead software demonstrations of *phyloregion* at the annual useR! or International Biogeography Society conference. 4) *Analysis vignettes:* We will create vignettes for common analytical workflows using *phyloregion* to facilitate easy usage of the package. Vignettes are tutorials written to show practical application of the functions in *phyloregion* under various scenarios. This means that all materials and products of this effort will be made freely available (see **Data Management Plan**). Each PI maintains an active blog for their R package on GitHub, which represents an enormous resource portal for the biogeographic and conservation community. For instance, GitHub now allows direct deployment of analysis vignettes directly to pkgdown³⁹, sometimes providing updates to the package's functions, other times describing entirely new methods, others are bugs or issues about our packages or R biogeographic packages. All the PIs have also been very active in the user community for R biogeography or phylogenetics by contributing to the email list-serves and blogs. For instance, Daru is active in the *R-sig-geo* and *Stack Overflow* communities, whereas Schliep is a regular contributor to the *R-sig-phylo* group (see *needs assessment*). All the PIs of this proposal intend to maintain this level of community engagement into the future. Finally, all the PIs have all been involved in running courses and workshops on biogeographic or phylogenetic methods in R (see **Broader Impacts**). In addition to instructing users on the proper use of software, such workshops serve the additional function of directly engaging user and developer. Often, students from workshops are much more willing to reach out to developers with

questions, comments and feedback after having taken a workshop with the developer than they might have been before. We intend to continue offering similar workshops in future as requested in this proposal.

Workflows for common software use cases will be developed and published via the *phyloregion* website¹¹¹. These use cases will be documented with sample data, and published in the RMarkdown format. This format is an open-source, extensible format that allows code to be stored alongside output and images to enhance reproducibility¹¹². Daru and Schliep have already been developing vignettes for the initial version of *phyloregion*¹¹¹. As stated in the section **Broader Impacts**, workshop participants will also document functions they generate with a real data use case. These will be included as vignettes in the package. Finally, we will develop a contributing guide for users to share their use cases. This contributing guide will include a code of conduct, data sharing guide, and formatting information. Wright has worked with similar contributing guides on the open source project RevBayes, and will use that project's guidelines as a basis.

H. Outcomes Assessment.

The efforts from **Objective 1** will be to add biome inference capabilities to *phyloregion* and R in general. **Objective 2** will significantly add to the visualization capabilities of *phyloregion* to aid assessment of biogeographic regions and macroecology. **Objective 2** will also result in the enhancement of *phyloregion* to pass objects between RevBayes and R. The main outcome of **Objective 3** will add new leading-edge tools for guiding conservation efforts which will reflect the three dimensions of phylodiversity: richness, divergence, or regularity. These objectives will be evaluated based on user feedback of blogposts and vignettes describing new functions, CRAN downloads, and citations in publications. In addition, students from the workshops will complete an evaluation at the end of each workshop and rate their experience with regard to the new knowledge/skills learned. Undergraduate students will be asked to rate their interest in continuing their education in graduate school before and after the workshop. The PI team will use these evaluations to optimize the package. All the products and methods developed in this study will be made open-source and freely distributed. Finally, we will continue to develop *phyloregion* using GitHub¹¹¹. All the contributors to this project already have pull request access meaning they can suggest source code and documentation changes to the package's repository on GitHub. This makes it easier to improve the package in real-time.

I. Sustainability.

All of the software products of this proposal will be built using an open-source development approach by hosting development versions on GitHub (e.g.³⁸). We will use continuous deployment (e.g., Travis CI¹¹³) to test that the development versions work with dependencies. We will follow best practices to document the source code (Roxygen) and apply unit tests to improve robustness of the code. We will upload stable versions periodically to the CRAN. Software associated with the proposal will also be published in ROpenSci, ensuring longer-term archival of the code. For instance, Wright's *treedata.table*³⁷ was published via ROpenSci. We will annotate software code and updates, and create documentation for all functionality and work flows. All the PIs of this project (Daru, Wright, Schliep and Bapst) have worked on the development and implementation of phylogeny and biogeographic methods in R or in other programming languages for over ten years. In the unlikely event that any investigator were to abandon their contribution, all our packages (*phyloregion*, *treedata.table*, *phangorn*, and *paleotree* including any software product of this grant) are/will be distributed free and open source under the GNU GPL software licenses, meaning that future developers could take over maintenance of the project without restriction. Produced software will include a contributing guide, with a code of conduct and explanations of how new users can interact with the code base. This will allow new contributors to enter the development process easily.

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**BUDGET JUSTIFICATION
DR. BARNABAS H. DARU
Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi**

Project Title: Collaborative Research: phyloregion, computational infrastructure for biogeographic regionalization and macroecology in the R computing environment

Project Dates: 1 June 2021–31 May 2024

This project has been proposed under the assumption that the COVID-19 pandemic and all related advisories and restrictions imposed at the federal, state, and local government levels, as well as by Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi will not be in effect at the time of award. If restrictions are in place at the time of award, changes in scope or alternative activities for contributing to the progress of the project may be proposed.

A. Senior Personnel

\$46,564 is requested for salary each year for years 1–3 for Dr. Barnabas Daru. PI Daru will oversee all aspects of this effort, directly supervise the postdoctoral fellow, and coordinate with the co-PIs on this effort. 3% yearly escalation is included in salary effective year 1.

B. Other Personnel

Postdoctoral Salary Support. Funds will pay a postdoctoral fellow to work on the project full time at 12 Cal Mos per year, in years 1-3; based on a monthly salary of \$3956.33. The postdoc will be based at TAMU-Corpus Christi and will focus on developing methods and tools for the three Objectives of the proposal. This researcher will assume the following responsibilities: developing new analytical methods; and preparing results for presentation and publication. *A 3% annual increase was included in the salary calculations effective year 2.*

Graduate Student. \$74,182 based on a monthly salary of \$4000 is requested to support one Ph.D. student for 3 academic years of the proposed project. The student will be responsible for developing biodiversity informatics tools for biome evolution, visualization, and conservation. The graduate student will participate in the workshops to be held in Corpus Christi TX (Y1 and Y3), and Hammond LA (Y3) (see below). The student will play an especially important role in software package release and sharing of analysis codes and vignettes, and take the lead on relevant publications. *A 3% annual increase was included in the salary calculations effective year 2*

TOTAL SALARIES: \$267,489

C. Fringe benefits

The TAMUCC fringe benefit rates are currently 18.5% for faculty and full benefit employees with insurance benefits at \$771/mo, 11% for graduate students with insurance benefits at \$558/mo.

Total fringe: \$86,349

Salaries + benefits = \$353,838

D. Equipment – N/A

E. PI Travel

PI Meetings followed by Annual Workshops. In each of years 1-3, this collaborative project will require travel support for (Co-)PI Daru, Wright, and the postdoctoral fellow to attend the proposed annual PI Meetings and Themed Annual Workshops to be held at TAMU-Corpus Christi and Southeastern Louisiana University (SLU). Each of these meetings will be 12 days in total. The PI Meeting will occur on the first two days and would involve only the PIs and postdoctoral fellow; the Annual Workshop would occur on the final 10 days. PI Daru will serve as a local host in Y1 and Y3, whereas co-PI Wright will be host in Y2, so travel support is budgeted only for senior personnel travelling from other locations. This budget includes RT airfare travel to and from the meeting location, ground transportation, lodging and subsistence, and incidentals.

For the purposes of this budget, we assume that meetings will be held at TAMU-Corpus Christi, TX in years 1 and 3. The TAMUCC/collaborators team would travel to Hammond, LA in year 2 (\$5,700).

[PI Wright's travel costs in years 1 and 3 are included in the SLU budget].

International Conference Travel: International travel in the amount of \$4,983 is requested for PI Daru, Postdoc and graduate student to attend and present findings from this project in one international conference in Y2, and Y3 (e.g., *useR!*, or *International Biogeography Society*). This international conference travel includes RT airfare to and from the conference location budgeted at \$1,200 for 3 participants totaling \$3,600; lodging @ \$97 for 3 nights for 3 participants totaling \$873; meals @ \$40 for 3 days for 3 participants totaling \$480; conference registration @ \$50 for 3 participants totaling \$300.

F. Participant Support

Travel for Annual Workshop. Each year, we budget funds to bring five student participants from across the US for each of the 10-day Annual Workshop held at TAMU-Corpus Christi (Y1 and Y3) and Hammond (Y2). This travel budget includes RT airfare to and from the meeting location budgeted at \$400 for 5 participants totaling \$2,000, ground transportation @ \$100 per each of the 5 participants totaling \$500, and meals for 2 travel days @ \$50 x 2 travel days per participant totaling \$500. This is under the assumption that these five more regional participants would be too far to travel easily and return within one day.

Subsistence for Annual Workshop: For the meeting at TAMU-Corpus Christi in Y1 and Y3, we request lodging accommodations for five or more regional participants, assuming some participants will be too far to travel easily and return within one day; thus, food and lodging are budgeted for 10 people at \$20/day/10 people/10 days at a field station/dorm at TAMUCC totaling \$2,000. Breakfasts costs are budgeted at \$13/person/10days/10participants totaling \$1,300. Dinner costs are calculated at \$23/day/10 people/10 days for a total of \$2,300.

G. Other Direct Costs

Materials and Supplies: N/A

Publication costs: Publication costs are requested in Y1, Y2 and Y3 (\$1,200 annually).

Consultant Services: N/A

Computer Services: N/A

Other:

Vivobook: Funds are requested to purchase 10 inexpensive ultrabooks (Asus Vivobook, or equivalent at approximately \$500/laptop) for use in the Laguna Madre biogeography workshop so that we are neither required to limit venues to sites with an equipped computer lab, nor restrict access to the course to students that can supply their own laptops.

Course Room Rental for Workshop: Estimated at \$1,500 for Y1 and Y3 that conference will be held at TAMUCC.

Mentoring Meeting for Workshop preparation and closing: \$750 for Y1 and Y3. This dinner will include participants and mentors to encourage and discuss future graduate school applications, program specific grad information and funding for early career researchers. It is a wrap up of the workshop.

Tuition Remission: Tuition for the graduate student is included as a mandatory benefit and has been streamlined to a flat rate based upon GRA effort. Tuition is charged at current rates for TAMUCC with a yearly escalation of 5%. Subtotal: **\$29,583**

Foreign Travel: We request funding for travel for collaborator Dr. Klaus Schliep from Graz University of Technology, Graz in Austria to attend the PI meetings and workshops in Y1 and Y3. Collaborator Schliep and PI Daru are the original developers of phyloregion software upon which this proposal rests and thus comprise the phyloregion team. Schliep will be involved in every aspect of the project as already indicated in the Project Description including teaching at the users' workshops to new methods development. International travel for collaborator Schliep in Y2 will be included in the SLU budget.

Conference Meals: Lunches and coffee breaks are included estimated at \$1,800 for the duration of the conference

Other for Annual Workshop: Materials are included for the participants at \$1,496 in Y1 and \$1,497 in Y2 that it is held at TAMUCC.

Travel for Baptst to TAMUCC: Travel is requested at \$400/year in years 1 and 3 for collaborator to travel from College Station, TX to Corpus Christi, TX

H. Total Direct costs are estimated at **\$436,580**.

- I. **Indirect costs** are estimated at \$148,470. TAMUCC's indirect costs are charged at rates of 37.5% in Y1, 38% in Y2 and Y3 of Modified Total Direct Costs (MTDC) for on-campus expenses.

Modified total direct costs shall exclude equipment, tuition, and any amount over the first \$25,000 of any subawards. The current Facilities & Administrative (F&A) Rate Agreement was signed on March 25th, 2019.

- J. **Total Direct and Indirect Costs** are estimated at **\$585,050**

BUDGET JUSTIFICATION
DR. APRIL WRIGHT
Southeastern Louisiana University

Project Title: Collaborative Research: phyloregion, computational infrastructure for biogeographic regionalization and macroecology in the R computing environment

Project Dates: 1 June 2021–31 May 2024

This project has been proposed under the assumption that the COVID-19 pandemic and all related advisories and restrictions imposed at the federal, state, and local government levels, as well as by Southeastern Louisiana University will not be in effect at the time of award. If restrictions are in place at the time of award, changes in scope or alternative activities for contributing to the progress of the project may be proposed.

A. Senior Personnel (\$41,205)

Co-PI Wright will contribute to research aims, as well as educational coordination on the workshops. During Years One, Two, and Three, Co-PI Wright requests three hours per semester (25%) as teaching buy-out time to focus on the research and to coordinate the development of the tutorials under the Broader Impacts aims into an undergraduate biogeography course. \$13,200 in Year One, \$13,728 in Year Two and \$14,277 in Year Three are requested for this buy-out. Salaries include a 4% cost of living increase if provided by Southeastern in accordance with an approved raise plan.

B. Other personnel (\$60,480)

\$20,160 is requested annually for undergraduate wages.

C. Fringe Benefits (\$15,658)

The Southeastern Louisiana University (Southeastern) fringe benefit rate is currently 38% for faculty and full benefit employees with insurance benefits at \$5,016 in Y1, \$5,217 in Y2, and \$5,425 in Y3.

TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES: \$101,685

Total Fringe: \$15,658

Salaries + Benefits = \$117,343

E. Travel (\$4,514)

1. PI Meetings/Annual Workshops (\$2,664): In each of Years 1-3, this collaborative project will require travel support for the PIs/senior personnel to attend the proposed annual meetings and workshops to be held at TAMU-Corpus Christi, TX (Y1 and Y3) and Southeastern-Hammond, LA (Y2). Each of these meetings will be 12 days in total. The PI Meeting will occur on the first two days and will involve only the PIs/senior personnel and postdoctoral fellow. The Annual Workshop will occur on the final ten days. One PI will serve as a local host each year, so travel support is budgeted only for senior personnel travelling from other locations. This budget includes RT airfare travel to and from the meeting location, ground transportation, lodging, subsistence, and incidentals for PI Wright. We anticipate that PI Wright will travel to TAMUCC for meetings in Year 1 (\$1,332) and Year 3 (\$1,332) See

Tables. In Year 2, the meeting/workshop will be hosted by Southeastern and held at Turtle

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Cove Environmental Research Station, which is a remote Southeastern Louisiana University research facility.

All travel will be in accordance with LA state travel guidelines PPM 49.

PI Travel Y1			Meeting at	TAMUCC
Travel	Unit Cost/Person	# Person	# Units	Notes
RT Airfare	\$300	1	1	From New Orleans
Lodging	\$20	1	11	11 nights at field station rate
Per diem allowance	\$46	1	2	75% of LA PPM 49 reimbursement rate
Meals	\$61	1	10	Daily meal rate per LA PPM 49
Ground trans.	\$50	1	2	Shuttle to/from airport
Incidentals	\$10	1	1	Wi-Fi, etc.
Total				\$1,332

PI Travel Y3			Meeting at	TAMUCC
Travel	Unit Cost/Person	# Person	# Units	Notes
RT Airfare	\$300	1	1	From New Orleans
Lodging	\$20	1	11	11 nights at field station rate
Per diem allowance	\$46	1	2	75% of LA PPM 49 reimbursement rate
Meals	\$61	1	10	Daily meal rate per LA PPM 49
Ground trans.	\$50	1	2	Shuttle to/from airport
Incidentals	\$10	1	1	Wi-Fi, etc.
Total				\$1,332

2. Foreign Travel (\$1,850): We request funding for travel for collaborator Dr. Klaus Schliep

from Graz University of Technology, Graz in Austria to attend the PI meeting and workshop in Y2 (\$1,850). Collaborator Schliep and PI Daru are the original developers of phyloregion software upon which this proposal rests and thus comprise the phyloregion team. Schliep will be involved in every aspect of the project as already indicated in the Project Description including teaching at the users' workshops to new methods development.

F. Participant Support (\$3,080)

In Year Two, Southeastern will host the annual workshop. Five student participants from across the US will attend the 10-day workshop. The participant support budget includes RT airfare ($\$400 \times 5 = \$2,000$), ground transportation to and from the meeting location ($\$100 \times 5$

= \$500), per diem allowance ($\$53/\text{day} \times 2 \text{ days} \times 5 = \530), and incidentals ($\$10 \times 5 = \50). An additional six students in close proximity to the host institution will also be invited.

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G. Other Direct Costs (\$16,169)

1. Materials and Supplies (\$3,863): Additionally, RStudio Server space is requested for Year Three in support of the Broader Impacts. PI Wright will teach a course based on the vignettes developed during the workshop (\$863). Funds are requested to supply laptops for undergraduate students working on the project (\$3,000 in Year One).

2. Publication Costs (\$2,400): Publication costs are requested in Years Two (\$1,200) and Three (\$1,200).

6. Other

Workshop Costs (\$9,906):

The Turtle Cove Environmental Research Station is a field research and educational/outreach facility of Southeastern Louisiana University and is located in the Lake Pontchartrain estuarine ecosystem. Because of its location at the upper end of this major estuary, Turtle Cove is within one hour by boat of various wetland environments and their aquatic counterparts. The classroom, lab space, and lodge on Pass Manchac are only accessible via boat. The surrounding wetlands can provide a wealth of research and educational experiences.

Turtle Cove can comfortably accommodate the PIs and student participants. The rental fee is \$150 per night for eleven nights (\$1,650).

Because of the remote location of Turtle Cove, meals must be transported to the station ($\$52$ per person per day $\times 15$ guests (11 students, 4 PIs) $\times 8$ days = \$6,240). Meal delivery is also necessary for the two days of planning that will occur only with the PIs/senior personnel ($\$52 \times 4$ guests $\times 2$ days = \$416).

Turtle Cove is accessible only by boat, and boat usage is priced at \$200 per day \times an estimated eight days (\$1,600).

H. Total Direct Costs are \$141,106.

I. The indirect cost rate for Southeastern is 38.6% of the Modified Total Direct Costs, which

include all direct costs with the exception of large equipment priced at \$5,000 or over (none in this proposal), any additional cost of subawards above the first \$25,000 (none in this proposal), participant costs (\$3,080), rental fees (\$1,650) and tuition (none in this proposal). MTDC for this proposal is \$136,376 for a total IDC of **\$52,641**.

J. Total Direct and Indirect Costs is \$193,747.

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT, AND OTHER RESOURCES

PI: BARNABAS H. DARU, TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY-CORPUS CHRISTI

The effort to be done at Texas A&M University, Corpus Christi (TAMUCC) will be computational in nature involving computer programming, tools and methods development and related analyses. Along these lines, researchers in the Daru lab have direct access to a Mac Pro with multi-core computing with 2.7 GHz 12-Core Intel Xeon E5 and 64 GB memory for simulations and programming projects. The Daru lab also has three additional dual-processor Apple iMac desktop computers with large-format displays, T1 Ethernet connections, and a printer, all devoted to bioinformatics, phylogenetic and biogeographic analyses. All researchers each have access to an Apple MacBook Pro for computational and general use, such as Microsoft Office applications and Adobe for generating documents, spreadsheets, and presentations; GIS and bioinformatic software for processing geographic data and editing of DNA sequences; and statistical software such as R and JMP for analyzing data. All computers have Internet access and are networked to the TAMUCC's High Performance Computing (HPC) cluster (see below).

Not directly related to the current project, the Daru lab is located in Tidal Hall, a new, state-of-the-art science research building on the campus of Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi. The laboratory is located in the same building with the Genetics Core Laboratory (below), a centralized sequencing facility with which Daru has direct access. The laboratory meets all the biosafety requirements of a BSL-1 laboratory for work with plants and has individual bench space for 10 students/researchers/technicians. Dr. Daru has a private office (150 ft²) located next to the research laboratory. Members of the Daru lab have individual cubicles located next to the research laboratory. Daru also serves as Curator of the Ruth O'Brien Herbarium at TAMUCC. The Herbarium is housed in a building adjacent to his laboratory building and includes office space as well as dedicated areas for digitization work station (lightbox, camera, computer), microscopy, voucher storage cabinets, and computation. The herbarium collection contains comprehensive plant records of the regional flora of the Texas coastal bend, and includes more than 11,000 plant specimens, photographic collections, a book collection, and a teaching collection.

Supercomputer

TAMUCC is equipped with a high performance-computing cluster that is used for data storage/backup and research purposes. Two full-time staff members, Mr. Phil Hale (Information Technology) and Mr. Thomas Merrick (College of Science and Engineering) maintain the cluster and assist researchers with usage. The Daru lab maintains a user forum for the supercomputer where information is shared and stored and that is moderated by Mr. Merrick and Mr. Krell.

The HPC cluster consists of 44 server nodes, each outfitted with 2 Intel Xeon E5 10 core processors. Four of the server nodes contain two NVidia GPUs each for CUDA programming. There is a 420 TB high performance Red Hat Cluster file server for work-space.

- *Compute Nodes:* The 40 compute nodes each contain two Xeon E5-2680v2 processors. These compute nodes each contain 256 GB of memory and 1 TB of local disk.
- *GPU Nodes:* The 4 GPU nodes each contain two Xeon E5-2660v3 processors and two NVidia Tesla K20X GPUs. These also contain 256 GB of memory and 1 TB of local disk.
- *File Systems:* The HPC cluster contains 10 TB of backed up disk space for program development and job procedures. There is also a 420 TB high performance Red Hat Cluster file system for large data sets and large work files.
- *Interconnect:* Nodes are interconnected with multiple Mellanox FDR InfiniBands in a non-blocking, topology/High Throughput Computing (HTC) system and Cyberinfrastructure for Data Management and analysis (CyVerse) for data storage/backup and research purposes.

MAJOR EQUIPMENT

The Daru laboratory is equipped with all equipment necessary to perform high throughput plant biogeography and molecular phylogenetic research. The specific pieces of equipment are listed here: freezers (1 -80 °C, 1 -20 °C) and refrigerators (2x 4 °C); one HEPA II biosafety cabinet (Labconco Corporation, Purifier Logic+; Thermo Scientific, 1300 Series A2); one portable laminar flow hood with prefilter and HEPA filters for remote processing of samples; Qubit fluorometer for DNA and RNA quantification; two PCR thermal cyclers (Biometra TOne 96-well Thermal Cycler); one DNA extraction cabinet with UV sterilization (Cleanair systems workstation) with dedicated pipettes; one platform shaker (Benchmark ORBi Shaker XL; Southwest); and one heatblock incubator. In addition, the Daru lab is equipped with glassware, stirring hotplates, vortexers, drying ovens, analytical balances, pH meter, chemicals, single/multichannel pipettes, Beckman Allegra X 30R Refrigerated Centrifuge with rotors for 96 well plates and tubes, high throughput bead-beater for 96 well DNA extractions, gel electrophoresis equipment, and other equipment routinely used for DNA/RNA extraction, PCR, and preparation of next-generation sequencing libraries.

OTHER RESOURCES

Laguna Madre Field Station: The Laguna Madre Field Station is TAMUCC's field station for the workshop in Y1 and Y3. The field station is located near Intracoastal Waterway Marker 83 (about 5 miles south of the JFK Causeway) in south Texas. The field station is accessible by boat, and managed under the direction of Dr. Kim Withers (see **letter of collaboration**). The field station is a complex of three buildings with four rooms for use as a: 1) classroom with kitchen, dining and meeting areas with projection equipment, 2) research/teaching laboratory, and 3) two dormitories that can sleep up to 20 students/researchers. The field station also has propane and electrical (generator and solar) utilities, a rainwater collection and freshwater storage system with showers, and restrooms.

TAMUCC Genomics Core Laboratory (GCL): Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi Genomics Core Laboratory offers access to state-of-the-art sequencing resources and services. Relevant to this proposal, the GCL maintains sequencing instruments, including a -80 Freezer, two -20 Freezers, two refrigerators, a Covaris M220 sonicator, a Bioruptor NGS sonicator, a Qiagen Tissue Lyser II, a Spectramax M3 plate reader, an Advanced Analytical Fragment Analyzer, a Labconco Refrigerated Centrivap, an ABI StepOnePlus RealTime PCR thermocycler, an Eppendorf epMotion 5075 low-throughput liquid handler, a Rainin BenchSmart 96 semi-automated pipetting system, a BluePippin automated DNA fragment size selector, an ABI 3730xl Genetic Analyzer, a Beckman Capillary Sequencer, a Milli-Q water system, a NanoDrop 2000c Spectrophotometer, a Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer, several Eppendorf and BioRad PCR machines, BioRad gel electrophoresis system with imager, several centrifuges, two plate centrifuges, several magnetic stands for paramagnetic bead cleanup, and several sets of Rainin single and multichannel pipettors, both automated and mechanical.

Services available include library preparation, sequencing and help with data processing. The GCL also provides competitively priced, high-quality, and fast-turnaround Sanger sequencing services.

Personnel. Daru will supervise the postdoctoral fellow based at the TAMUCC. Co-PI Wright, and collaborators Schliep and Bapst will support mentorship and supervisory roles to complete the **Objectives** of the proposal. As we detail in the proposal, Daru and Schliep will lead **Objectives 1, 2, and 3**, Bapst will lead **Objective 2**, and Wright will lead **Objectives 1 and 2**. All PIs will collaborate on these three **Objectives**. Daru will serve as the project liaison with the TAMUCC STEM Learning Center to

translate best practices in inclusivity to all project team members. He also will serve as liaison between the TAMUCC-based diversity/inclusion initiatives and the project as a whole, ensuring that all aspects of commitment to fostering diversity in STEM is fulfilled. With his team he will present the findings of this work, share protocols, release data, and submit manuscripts during the timeframe of the project. Overall Daru will take responsibility for integration among the team members to achieve all goals of the proposed research.

FACILITIES, EQUIPMENT, AND OTHER RESOURCES

PI: April M. Wright, Southeastern Louisiana University

The effort to be done at Southeastern Louisiana University will be computational in nature involving computer programming, tools and methods development and related analyses. Along these lines, researchers in the Wright lab have direct access to 3 Linux desktop machines with 1 TB memory and 64 GB RAM. Monitors and peripherals are present for all computers. The Wright lab also has several large-format displays, ethernet and Wi-Fi connections, and printers. These resources are for any and all Wright lab personnel. All researchers each have access to an Linux laptops for computational and general use, such as Microsoft Office applications and Adobe for generating documents, spreadsheets, and presentations; GIS and bioinformatic software for processing geographic data and editing of DNA sequences; and statistical software such as R and JMP for analyzing data. All computers have Internet access and are networked to the State of Louisiana's High Performance Computing (HPC) cluster, The Louisiana Optical Network Infrastructure (LONI) (see below).

Not directly related to the current project, the Wright lab is located in Thelma Ryan Hall, on the main campus of Southeastern in Hammond, LA. Dr. Wright has a private office located down the hall from the research laboratory. Members of the Wright lab have desk space in the research laboratory.

Supercomputer

Southeastern is equipped with a high performance-computing cluster that is used for data storage/backup and research purposes (for full descriptions of available services see: <https://loni.org/>). QB2 came on-line 5 Nov 2014. It is a 1.5 Petaflop peak performance cluster containing 504 compute nodes with 960 NVIDIA Tesla K20x GPU's, and over 10,000 Intel Xeon processing cores. The system is housed in the state's Information Systems Building (ISB), located in Baton Rouge.

- *Compute Nodes*: The 352 compute nodes each with two 10-core 2.8 GHz E5-2680v2 Xeon processors. These compute notes each contain 64 GB of memory and 500 GB of local disk.
- *File Systems*: The HPC cluster contains 100 TB of backed up disk space for program development and job procedures.
- *Access*: LONI is accessed via SSH from Wright lab or personal machines.

MAJOR EQUIPMENT

The Wright lab is entirely dry lab. Several collaboration tables with in-desk power and HDMI hook ups for code and screen sharing are equipped in the lab.

OTHER RESOURCES

Turtle Cove: Turtle Cove is Southeastern's field station for the workshop in Year Two. Turtle Cove is located on Pass Manchac in Manchac, LA. The field station is access via boat, which will be piloted by Rob Moreau, the director of the Turtle Cove (see letter of collaboration) or caretaker Hayden Reno. The field station sleeps 18 and is equipped with multiple classrooms with power and projection equipment.

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

This proposal requests funding to develop and expand the *phyloregion* R package for the analysis of biogeographic regionalization and macroecology, tailored for macroecological datasets and mega phylogenies. Because the goal of this proposal is to develop computational tools and methods in R, the main products of this project will be computer code programmed in the scientific computing language, R (R Core Team 2020), publications, improved documentation and vignettes for easy access.

- 1) **Computer codes.** The proposed project will generate several new computer codes in the R scientific computing environment. These codes will be added to our open-source R package *phyloregion* through the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN). Apart from getting the latest version of *phyloregion*, CRAN also keeps a record of previous versions of a package. This feature is useful especially for reproducibility of previous researches. The development version of *phyloregion* is also freely available on Github, where one can find the latest version of the package. This is important for collaboration involving more researchers because GitHub has a built-in revision control that allows working collaboratively on a project.
- 2) **Publications and dissemination:** All the outcomes of the efforts in this project will be prepared and disseminated to the scientific community through peer-reviewed publications, workshops and courses, and conference presentations.
- 3) **Vignettes and improved documentation:** All vignettes and documentation will be made available through the *phyloregion* pkgdown website.
- 4) **Intellectual property:** The PIs of this project do not seek intellectual property protection on any findings resulting from this project. All data generated, codes and vignettes will be made available to the community promptly as indicated above.
- 5) **Time table of data release.** All data and code will be released upon publication and no later than two years of the completion of this grant.
- 6) **Simulated data:** Although no empirical data will be generated on this project, any simulated data will be produced to verify the new methods that will be developed. We will then deposit simulated scripts and data in public repositories including Dryad.

POSTDOCTORAL MENTORING PLAN

This proposal will support one postdoctoral fellow who will be based at Texas A&M University, Corpus Christi (TAMUCC) and will play a key role on the project. PIs Daru, Wright, Schliep and Bapst will serve as mentors for this postdoc, who will be immediately supervised by Daru. The mentoring of the postdoctoral fellow will center on various activities at various scales: individual, departmental and institutional. The PIs and postdoctoral fellow will work together to establish and implement an individualized mentoring plan based on the postdoctoral fellow's career goals. The postdoctoral fellow's involvement will be to focus on the three main **Objectives** of the proposal. The researcher will play a central role in all the scientific work of this proposal, and assume the following responsibilities: developing new biogeography methods; programming method in R; conducting and analyzing numerical simulations; and preparing results for publication. In addition, the postdoc will be central to the proposed annual workshops, and will be instrumental to the selection of students, and to work side-by-side with the PIs to prepare and execute each of these events. We emphasize that **all members of the project leadership team will interact with this early-career scientist**, providing a unique multi-disciplinary and multi-institutional mentorship opportunity. Ultimately, our goal for postdoctoral mentorship is to train successful, independent research scientists. Along these lines, we anticipate mentorship in the following specific areas:

- **Professional development.** Given the extremely competitive academic job market, the PI team will schedule monthly meetings with the postdoctoral researchers in the Daru lab to review career development issues and goals. We will review curriculum vitae preparation, academic job applications, and job interviews. We will arrange joint meeting with other junior and senior faculty at TAMUCC for additional professional advising.
- **Regular meetings:** The postdoctoral fellow will attend weekly seminars and will participate in weekly lab meetings, where lab members and associates regularly workshop ideas, datasets, and manuscripts, and have opportunities to practice presentation skills in a collegial, supportive academic environment.
- **Grant Writing Skills:** The postdoctoral fellow will be given the opportunity to participate in grant writing seminars especially offered regularly by the Division of Research and Innovation at TAMUCC.
- **Education and outreach:** This grant has an extensive set of educational programs. The postdoctoral researcher hired for this grant will co-teach the Laguna Madre biogeography-method users workshop in years 1 and 3. The fellow will also TA at the workshop in Turtle Cove Field Station, Louisiana in Year 2. The PI team will work closely with the postdoc to organize and administer all the workshops of the grant. By participating in the workshops, the postdoc will gain experience in teaching, organization, and student management.
- **Mentoring Skills:** The postdoctoral fellow will have the opportunity to mentor and supervise undergraduate students in the PI's laboratory. Depending on prior interests and experience, undergraduate projects supervised by the postdocs of this grant proposal might involve empirical data analysis using new biogeography methods, or code development for the *phyloregion* package.
- **Publication and presentations:** Finally, the postdoctoral fellow will co-author most of the publications produced by this grant. The PI team will give the postdoctoral fellow extensive guidance on writing and article submission. We will also encourage (and subsidize) postdocs supported by this grant to attend at least one annual scientific meeting, such as the *International Biogeography Society* or *UseR!* meeting, each year.

Success of the Mentoring Plan will be evaluated by tracking the progress that the postdoctoral candidate makes toward their research and career goals.